

Evaluation of Apache Knox integration with CERN SSO

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of data management and security, the integration of authentication and authorization mechanisms is crucial for ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive information. This project aims to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating Apache Knox with the Single Sign-On (SSO) at CERN.

The primary objective of this project is to evaluate the integration of Apache Knox, an open-source gateway for securing and centralizing access to multiple Hadoop clusters, with the CERN Single Sign-On infrastructure. The goal is to enhance the security and streamline the authentication process for accessing distributed data from Hadoop and HBase clusters hosted centrally at CERN. The successful integration of Apache Knox with CERN SSO can provide CERN with a robust and secure solution for managing access to distributed data, thereby improving user data security.

As an integral part of this project, Apache Knox will be deployed and evaluated within a controlled development environment. This evaluation seeks to ascertain its compatibility with various components of the Hadoop Ecosystem at CERN, including HDFS, Yarn, HBase, MapReduce, and Spark History Server. Special emphasis will be placed on configuring the SSO gateway, integrating with CERN SSO (e.g., with Keycloak and application portal entities), and testing the high availability mode, along with authorization-based API calls to services like the webHDFS REST API.

ABSTRACT

This project explores the implementation of Apache Knox to secure various Hadoop web services, specifically HBaseUI, YARNUI, HDFSUI, and the Spark History Server, within the context of a summer internship at CERN. The primary goal was to transition from the existing SPNEGO-based security framework to an Apache Knox-based solution, addressing the limitations of SPNEGO while enhancing the security and user experience for accessing Hadoop services.

SPNEGO, which relies on Kerberos tickets for authentication, presents several challenges, including complex browser configurations, inconsistent user experiences, and frequent access issues across different browsers. These issues often lead to a high volume of support requests, burdening the IT support team.

Apache Knox, by contrast, offers a single point of authentication and access for Hadoop services, simplifying the security architecture and improving accessibility. Knox's topology-based configuration and customizable rewrite rules allow for flexible protection of services, providing a more consistent and user-friendly experience. However, the project also addresses the complexities of the initial setup, the performance overhead introduced by Knox, and the importance of ensuring high availability of the gateway.

The project involved configuring Knox, setting up secure access through CERN's OIDC-based SSO, and protecting key Hadoop services. Additionally, it explored overcoming challenges in securing the Spark History Server, which required custom proxy setups due to CORS-related issues. The implementation was further enhanced by automating the configuration and deployment process using Puppet, and by building RPM packages to streamline future updates and maintenance. Comprehensive monitoring was established to ensure the reliability and performance of the secured services.

Lastly, the project concluded with the creation of a detailed poster summarizing the work, which highlights the practical benefits of transitioning to Apache Knox. The results demonstrate that while Knox introduces some setup complexity initially, it significantly streamlines security management and access control for Hadoop services, ultimately offering a more reliable and user-friendly solution than SPNEGO.

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INTRODUCTION

This documentation serves as a guide to set up Apache Knox to protect HBaseUI YARNUI HDFSUI and Spark history Server in the context of the Summer Internship project of Thomas Mauran.

Gitlab repo rpm: [here](#) Gitlab repo IT Module branch knox_sso_setup: [here](#)

Introduction

In this documentation, we will explore the setup of Apache Knox to secure HBaseUI, YARNUI, HDFSUI, and the Spark History Server within the context of my summer internship project at CERN. The primary objective is to transition from the existing SPNEGO-based security framework to an Apache Knox-based solution. This transition aims to address the shortcomings of SPNEGO, streamline authentication processes, and enhance the user experience for accessing Hadoop services.

SPNEGO current state and issues

Currently the security is handled by SPNEGO (Simple and Protected GSSAPI Negotiation Mechanism) which uses Kerberos tickets to make sure users are logged in and have the right to access both WEBUIs and APIs.

This system works in theory, but has multiple flaws in practice. In the actual way of setting up SPNEGO, in reality every user must modify some policy in its own browser to make SPNEGO work. Those instructions are available [here](#) and even though it doesn't seem to be easy at first it's not that easy to do.

The major problem being that even if you correctly configured your browser, it might not even work on some services. For example, on Firefox a lot of pages on almost all the services returns errors making them unavailable. To solve this, you basically have to change your browser, which is not handy at all. And as computer scientist these ideas to test it in another browser might be easy to get but for a regular user who took already a lot of time to configure it's browser it seems impossible to figure out what is the source root of the problem, inevitably leading in the creation of support tickets which in the end overloads the managing team with problems they shouldn't have to deal with.

Apache Knox as a solution

Apache Knox Gateway is a system that provides a single point of authentication and access for Apache Hadoop services in a cluster. It provides a single point of access for all REST and HTTP interactions with Apache Hadoop clusters.

Knox uses a system of topology files allowing you to protect different services. This topology like architecture is pretty easy to maintain and user-friendly after getting a bit of experience with it.

In the same direction, one of Apache Knox's great strengths is its customizability. If you have to add another custom REST service you can simply write rewrite rules for it, and it will work out of the box. I had to tweak some of those rewrite rules on some services for the purpose of this deployment and once you understand the process it's easy to debug and customize.

Here is a typical Knox architecture, showcasing the token verification and services behind a proxy

Pros and cons of Knox vs SPNEGO

Pros of Knox:

1. **Single Point of Access:** Knox provides a centralized gateway for all Hadoop services, simplifying access management and reducing the complexity of dealing with multiple endpoints.
2. **Ease of Use:** Once set up, Knox requires minimal configuration on the client-side, eliminating the need for users to modify their browser settings.
3. **Customizability:** Knox's topology files and rewrite rules allow for flexible and easy customization to protect various services, including custom REST services.
4. **Consistent User Experience:** Knox ensures a more consistent and reliable user experience across different browsers and services using CERN SSO, reducing the likelihood of access issues.

Cons of Knox:

1. **Initial Setup Complexity:** Setting up Knox for the first time can be complex and time-consuming, requiring a good understanding of the system and its configuration.
2. **Performance Overhead:** Introducing an additional gateway layer may introduce some performance overhead, potentially impacting the response time of protected services.

3. **Dependency on Gateway:** All traffic to Hadoop services passes through the Knox Gateway, creating a single point of failure. Ensuring high availability of the gateway is crucial.

Pros of SPNEGO:

1. **Integrated with Kerberos:** SPNEGO leverages Kerberos authentication, which is already widely used and trusted for secure authentication in many enterprise environments.
2. **Direct Service Access:** Users can directly access services without needing an additional gateway layer, which can simplify the architecture and reduce potential bottlenecks.
3. **Low Overhead:** Without the need for an intermediary gateway, SPNEGO can potentially offer lower latency and better performance for direct service access.

Cons of SPNEGO:

1. **Browser Configuration:** Users must configure their browsers to support SPNEGO, which can be complex and inconsistent across different browsers and versions.
2. **Inconsistent User Experience:** Even with proper configuration, SPNEGO may not work consistently across all services and browsers, leading to frequent access issues.
3. **Support Burden:** The need for user-side configuration and troubleshooting can lead to a high volume of support tickets, placing a burden on the IT support team.
4. **Limited Customization:** SPNEGO does not offer the same level of flexibility and customizability for protecting and managing access to various services as Knox does.

Basic setup of Apache Knox

Prerequisites

- Make sure you are running on Java **8** or **11**.
- The following examples will use **123456** as a password, obviously do not use that as a password

Binary download

First, we need to download the binary files available [here](#) as **Gateway Server Binary 2.0.0**. Make sure you then unzip the file and work from inside of it.

Installation

Once downloaded (or built) you will have access to a `./bin` folder containing your binaries.

Including:

- **knoxcli.sh**: The main command line interface that we will use to interact with the Knox configuration
- **gateway.sh**: The cli to start - stop - status the gateway

Another important folder is `./logs` which is where you will find the very useful log files of both `knoxcli` the gateway as well as your Knox topology files.

Create the master secret

```
/usr/hdp/knox/bin/knoxcli.sh create-master --master 123456 --force
```

This command will generate a master secret for the Knox server. The master secret is used to encrypt the passwords in the topology files and is stored in `./data/security/master` file

keystore files

Those commands might be obsolete if you are using the generated puppet keystores or the one provided by `tbag`

One important thing to make sure you will be able to start the gateway is to ensure you have both `__gateway-credentials.jceks` and `gateway.jks`.

- **__gateway-credentials.jceks**: This is the credential store for the gateway itself and you will want to add a credential to this that protects the private key passphrase used when you import the key pair into the identity store. This is done with `knoxcli.sh create-alias gateway-identity-passphrase --value {value}`.
- **gateway.jks**: This is the identity keystore for the Knox Gateway and needs the public and private keys as well as any signing certs. (see apache docs) The expected alias for the certificate is `gateway-identity`.

Creation of the `__gateway-credentials.jceks` file

```
keytool -genseckey -alias gateway-credentials -keyalg AES -keysize 256 -keypass 123456
-storepass 123456 -keystore /usr/hdp/knox/data/security/keystores/__gateway-credentials.jceks
-storetype JCEKS
```

This command will create the JCEKS store

You must also add an alias in this file by using the following command

```
/usr/hdp/knox/bin/knoxcli.sh create-alias gateway-identity-passphrase
--value 123456
```

You may want to see what is inside the store and you could do that using the following command (make sure you enter the password you set before in our case 123456):

```
keytool -v -list -storetype JCEKS -keystore
/usr/hdp/knox/data/security/keystores/__gateway-credentials.jceks
```

This is what should be displayed at this point:

```
[tmauran@ithdpdev-ekleszcz01 knox-2.0.0]$ keytool -v -list -storetype JCEKS
-keystore data/security/keystores/__gateway-credentials.jceks

Enter keystore password:

Keystore type: JCEKS

Keystore provider: SunJCE

Your keystore contains 2 entries

Alias name: gateway-credentials

Creation date: Jul 3, 2024

Entry type: SecretKeyEntry

*****

*****

Alias name: gateway-identity-passphrase

Creation date: Jul 4, 2024

Entry type: SecretKeyEntry

*****

*****
```

Warning:

The JCEKS keystore uses a proprietary format. It is recommended to migrate to PKCS12 which is an industry standard format using "keytool -importkeystore -srckeystore /usr/hdp/knox/data/security/kestores/__gateway-credentials.jceks -destkeystore /usr/hdp/knox/data/security/kestores/__gateway-credentials.jceks -deststoretype pkcs12".

Creation of the gateway.jks file

```
keytool -genkey -alias gateway-identity -keyalg RSA -keysize 2048 -keypass 123456 -storepass 123456 -keystore /usr/hdp/knox/data/security/kestores/gateway.jks -dname "CN=Knox, OU= , O=CERN, L=Meyrin, ST=Geneva, C=Switzerland"
```

This command will create the jks store which contains a self signed certificate

We create this by hand instead of using the `knoxcli create-cert` command because in java 11 the `md5WithRSAEncryption` package will provoke an error since it got removed.

You may want to see what is inside the store and you could do that using the following command (make sure you enter the password you set before in our case 123456):

```
keytool -v -list -storetype jks -keystore data/security/kestores/gateway.jks
```

This is what should be displayed at this point:

```
[tmauran@ithdpdev-ekleszcz01 knox-2.0.0]$ keytool -v -list -storetype jks -keystore data/security/kestores/gateway.jks

Enter keystore password:

Keystore type: JKS

Keystore provider: SUN
```

```

Your keystore contains 1 entry

Alias name: gateway-identity
Creation date: Jul 4, 2024
Entry type: PrivateKeyEntry
Certificate chain length: 1
Certificate[1]:
Owner: CN=Unknown, OU=Unknown, O=Unknown, L=Unknown, ST=Unknown, C=Unknown
Issuer: CN=Unknown, OU=Unknown, O=Unknown, L=Unknown, ST=Unknown, C=Unknown
Serial number: 4398041b
Valid from: Thu Jul 04 08:26:48 CEST 2024 until: Wed Oct 02 08:26:48 CEST 2024
Certificate fingerprints:

Signature algorithm name: SHA256withRSA
Subject Public Key Algorithm: 2048-bit RSA key
Version: 3
Extensions:
#1: ObjectId: 2.5.29.14 Criticality=false
SubjectKeyIdentifier [
KeyIdentifier [
]
]

*****
*****

```

Obviously some values like the fingerprint and date may differ on yours.

Running the gateway

You shall now have the following architecture at this point

```
/usr/hdp/knox/
├── data/
│   ├── security/
│       ├── keystores/
│           ├── gateway.jks
│           └── __gateway-credentials.jceks
```

You can now try to run the gateway using the following command:

```
./bin/gateway.sh start
```

It may take some times but then you should receive this message:

```
[tmauran@ithdpdev-ekleszcz01 Knox-2.0.0]$ ./bin/gateway.sh start
```

Starting Gateway succeeded with PID 308779.

If the gateway failed to start you shall also get a corresponding message and start to investigate in the *logs/gateway.log* or *logs/gateway.err* files.

Making our first topology file

By default Knox comes in with multiple topologies in *conf/topologies* such as:

admin.xml, *homepage.xml*, *manager.xml*, *metadata.xml*, *sandbox.xml*.

Those topologies might be handy for debugging your *knoxsso.xml* file since they should be working out of the box.

Each file in the */conf/topologies/<name>.xml* will be mapped in the URI for example here <https://host/gateway/name>

Setting up the keycloak client (Application portal)

CERN uses the [application portal](#) to manage OIDC clients.

Create a new application with the following attributes:

- Application Identifier: Knox
- Name: Knox
- Description: Knox POC
- Home page: <http://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/> (or your cluster hostname)
- Category: Test
- Admin group: None

Then next step: SSO Registration:

- Redirect URI(s): <https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/>* (change it with your cluster hostname)
- Base URL: <https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/>

Make sure you **uncheck** the 2 checkboxes for the client secret configuration.

You should end up with the client id and the client secret make sure you save those so we can use it in the `knoxsso.xml` file.

Setting up the `knoxsso.xml` file

The `knoxsso.xml` file serves as a configuration file for the Knox Single Sign-On (SSO).

Remove the current text inside of it and paste this configuration file: [knoxsso.xml](#)

Make sure you modify the following fields:

- `pac4j.callbackUrl` ->
`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/knoxsso/api/v1/webssso`
- `cas.loginUrl` ->
`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/knoxsso/api/v1/webssso/login`
- `oidc.id` -> The ID you acquired in the [Setting up the keycloak client \(Application portal\)](#)
- `oidc.secret` -> The OIDC secret you acquired in the [Setting up the keycloak client \(Application portal\)](#)
- `oidc.discoveryUri` -> available [here](#) in the *OIDC well-known configuration URLs* file
- Add your correct hostname regex to the whitelist (make sure you include the `hdfs / hbase` etc port otherwise you will get a 400 error)

Make sure you stop and start the gateway after each modification of a topology.

If we wanna try out configuration we can use the manager topology mentioned before. Out of the box this topology should create the following endpoint.

Try accessing to the following endpoint (change the hostname):

`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/manager/admin-ui/`

After signing in to the CERN SSO you should access the following page:

If that is not the case make sure your `knoxsso.xml` file is filled with the correct information and check the logs/ files.

Setting up the `gateway-site.xml` file

Here is the working `gateway-site.xml` that you need to use instead of the one in `conf/gateway-site.xml`

Writing our first `default.xml` file

We are going to write a new file named `default.xml` from which we will add all our services later on.

Here is an example of `default.xml` file: [default.xml](#)

Make sure you change the following values:

- sso.authentication.provider.url ->
`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/knoxsso/api/v1/websso`
- WEBHDFS -> `https://<namenode host>:50070/webhdfs`

Make sure you stop and start the gateway again.

To test our configuration we are going to add a folder and a file in our hdfs, in my case /user/tmauran/hello.txt

You shall now have access to the following url and get your file downloaded after logging in CERN SSO page:

`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/default/webhdfs/v1/<your>/<path>?op=OPEN`

If that is not the case make sure your default.xml file is filled with the correct information and check the logs/ files.

Remove the SPNEGO conf from core-site.xml and hdfs-site.xml

To disable SPNEGO we had to comment parts related to it in both `/etc/hadoop/conf/core-site.xml` and `/etc/hadoop/conf/hdfs-site.xml`.

Here is an example of working [core-site.xml](#)

In `/etc/hadoop/conf/hdfs-site.xml` we will comment the following properties:

- `dfs.web.authentication.kerberos.principal`
- `dfs.web.authentication.kerberos.keytab`
- `dfs.journalnode.kerberos.internal.spnego.principal`

Protection of the hadoop cluster services using Knox

Apache Knox got a set of already defined rewrite and services available in data/services.

Those are then usable in the topology files as follows

HDFS WebUI

```
<service>
  <role>HDFSUI</role>
  <version>2.7.0</version>
  <url>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:50070</url>
</service>
```

To protect each service we need to enable [multiple things](#) in the `core-site.xml` config.

First of all make sure you have access to the following homepage UI:

`https://<hostname>:8443/gateway/homepage/home/`

If you get prompted a login page make sure you started the demo LDAP server

The default credentials are **username:** guest **password:** guest-password

You should end up on something looking like that:

You must now download the PEM TLS certificate that we are gonna need in our core-site configuration. You can directly get the certificate using the following command:
`/usr/hdp/knox/bin/knoxcli.sh export-cert --type pem`

In `core-site.xml` add the following things:

```
<!-- Knox Security -->

<property>
  <name>hadoop.http.authentication.type</name>
  <value>org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.JWTRedirectAuthentic
ationHandler</value>
</property>

<property>
  <name>hadoop.http.authentication.authentication.provider.url</name>
  <value>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/gateway/knoxssso/api/v1/webss
so</value>
</property>

<property>
  <name>hadoop.http.authentication.public.key.pem</name>
  <value><Your public token from the .pem file></value>
</property>
```

You should now not be able to directly access hdfs without getting logged in

YARN WebUI

```
<service>
  <role>YARNUI</role>
  <url>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8088</url>
</service>
```

To enable YARNUI make sure you defined the YARN service.

To fix the CSS problem you might encounter on the `:8443/gateway/default/yarn` you need to change this line in `data/services/yarnui/2.7.0/rewrite.xml`

What this does is directly go on the server URL to get the static files. Yarn UI will by default be protected if you applied the HDFS configuration mentioned above in `core-site.xml`

Use the following rewrite rules: [rules](#)

Spark history

```
<service>
  <role>SPARK3HISTORYUI</role>
  <url>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:18080</url>
</service>
```

Use the following rewrite rules: [rules](#)

To secure enable Spark UI redirection to Knox when trying to directly access it you will have to add the following properties in `/etc/spark/conf/spark-defaults.conf`:

[spark-default.conf](#)

```
spark.org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter.
param.kerberos.principal=<Host principal>

spark.org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter.
param.kerberos.keytab=<Path to the keytab>

spark.ui.filters=org.apache.spark.deploy.yarn.YarnProxyRedirectFilter,org.ap
ache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter

spark.org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter.
param.type
org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.JWTRedirectAuthenticationHa
ndler

spark.org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter.
param.authentication.provider.url https://<Knox
host>:8443/gateway/knoxssso/api/v1/websso
```

```
spark.org.apache.hadoop.security.authentication.server.AuthenticationFilter.
param.public.key.pem=<Your pem key>
```

The PEM key is the one you retrieved in the [HDFS part](#). Make sure you remove every `\n` otherwise you will get an error saying that your PEM key is corrupted.

We also need to use the new `hadoop-client-api-3.3.6.jar` instead of `3.3.4`, to do so

```
cp /usr/hdp/hadoop/share/hadoop/common/lib/hadoop-auth-3.3.6.jar
/usr/hdp/spark/jars/
```

#then remove the 3.3.4 one

```
rm -rf /usr/hdp/spark/jars/hadoop-auth-3.3.4.jar

rm -rf /usr/hdp/spark/jars/hadoop-client-api-3.3.4.jar
```

Spark needs a proxy to work

As Spark History UI was causing some issues when being proxied by Knox (302 CORS error on the jquery api call) we had to put in place 2 small proxies in front of each spark instance. The goal of those are to redirect to either spark instance using the capability of the HTML redirect tag. This mechanism is exactly the one featured in HDFS, and this is why we automatically get redirected to the namenode when clicking on HDFS in the homepage.

```
# Install nginx from yum
yum install nginx

# From the gitlab content do the following

# Copy the nginx.conf in /etc/nginx/nginx.conf

# Copy the index.html in /usr/share/nginx/html/index.html

# Add the hostnames in /usr/share/nginx/html/spark-hostnames

# We save the hostname of the server on the /hostname route for the script
```

```
to work

hostname > /usr/share/nginx/html/hostname

sudo mkdir -p /etc/pki/nginx
# Here we could use the custom certificate generated as for the other
services but for a matter of time saving we just another one
sudo openssl req -new -x509 -nodes -days 3650 -newkey rsa:2048 -keyout
/etc/pki/nginx/server.key -out /etc/pki/nginx/server.crt -subj
"/C=US/ST=California/L=San Francisco/O=My
Company/CN=your_domain.com/emailAddress=your_email@example.com"

# Start nginx using

nginx
```

So basically the proxy is a simple NGINX server with one index.html containing the following tag:

```
<meta http-equiv="REFRESH"
content="0;url=https://hdp-ekleszcz-dev-gateway.cern.ch:18080" />
```

This tag allows us to force the redirection to the Spark UI, it was inspired of what is done in the Hadoop source code where a similar thing is happening. Code available [here](#)

We don't know why spark blocks CORS doing this weird 302 error and here are the forum / mailing list follow-ups for this issue:

Cloudera forum

- [Error with Pac4j Query param](#)
- [Spark history CORS header access control allow origin](#)
- [Spark history UI for apache Knox](#)

Mailing list threads

- [Force redirect to a service instead of proxying](#)
- [Error with Pac4j provider on query param of original URL](#)
- [Error with Sparkhistory UI](#)

HBase

Make sure you remove the following properties to disable simply pass the Kerberos UI to simple

```
<property>
  <name>hbase.security.authentication</name>
  <value>simple</value>
</property>

<property>
  <name>hbase.security.authentication.ui</name>
  <value>simple</value>
</property>
<property>
  <name>hbase.security.authentication</name>
  <value>simple</value>
</property>
```

Currently, HBase doesn't provide any mechanism to redirect to a JWT provider, this is currently a work in progress but meaning to protect HBase we need to protect it behind the firewall and make it inaccessible from outside. This way, the only working path is to go through Knox proxy.

[JIRA ticket](#)

Make sure you remove port 60010 from the whitelist NFT ports to make it inaccessible from outside.

We are gonna replace this 60010 rule with one allowing only the IP of the other nodes to that port. That way the port will be closed online but when Knox tries to proxy request from the master node to the backup node it will be able to do so and display the corresponding UI.

To do so we are gonna use this command:

```
nft add rule inet filter default_in ip saddr @cluster_hg_ipset4 tcp dport
60010 accept

nft add rule inet filter default_in ip6 saddr @cluster_hg_ipset6 tcp dport
60010 accept
```

Make sure you do it on both master nodes.

Then do the same for the region servers.

Remove the port 16030 and add those rules:

```
nft add rule inet filter default_in ip saddr @cluster_hg_ipset4 tcp dport
16030 accept

nft add rule inet filter default_in ip6 saddr @cluster_hg_ipset6 tcp dport
16030 accept
```

To add the new service in the topology we need to declare a service with the HBASEUI role as following:

```
<service>
  <role>HBASEUI</role>
  <url>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:60010</url>
</service>
```

Then the service will be accessible with the following URL, make sure you replace the host and port with the master one, this is currently not very handy but could be reworked in the end.

<https://<knox-host>:8443/gateway/default/hbase/webui/master?host=ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch&port=60010>

In the end HBase rewrite rules will be the trickiest one to maintain, since we not only need to maintain the first page after the quick link access but also all the sub pages of the whole UI.

Map reduce history

Add this service in the default topology

```
<service>
  <role>JOBHISTORYUI</role>
  <url>https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:19888</url>
</service>
```

As for the other services make sure you update the whitelist port in the gateway-site.xml file to allow 19888. You will also need to change the rewrite files to the one on GitLab as some rules are not correct in the current version

REST APIs

Curling the endpoints

To CURL the different services, we need to use the CERN [auth-get-sso-cookie](#) tool.

⚠ auth-get-sso-cookie doesn't work with account who have 2FA activated, to use it you will need to be

Apache Knox adds a cookie called `hadoop-jwt` when you connect to sso, one thing is that Kerberized Hadoop environment also add another cookie called `hadoop-auth` that is mandatory to be able to CURL those endpoints.

To acquire both of those cookies we are gonna be using the `auth-get-sso-cookie` on the namenode endpoint which will provide us those 2 cookies

```
auth-get-sso-cookie -vv -u "https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:50070/" -o auth
```

here we are storing the cookie in the auth file

you can `cat` this file to make sure you have both `hadoop-jwt` and `Hadoop-auth`, if it's not the case make sure you are using the right Kerberos ticket. `kdestroy` and `kinit` a new one on an account which doesn't have 2FA (`hbuilder` for example).

Once you have the auth file you can CURL each of the endpoint using the `-Lb` flag (`-L` allows relocation following, and is mandatory while `-b` allows you to pass a cookie file).

CURL examples

```
# Namenode

curl -Lb auth
"https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:50070/dfshealth.html#tab-overview"

# Yarn

curl -Lb auth "https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8088"

curl -Lb auth
"https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/gateway/default/yarn"

# HBase

curl -Lb auth
"https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/gateway/default/hbase/webui/master
??&host=ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch&port=60010"

# Mapreduce history
```

```
curl -Lb auth
"https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/gateway/default/jobhistory/"

# SparkhistoryUI

# For Spark we will need to regenerate a cookie with auth-get-sso-cookie but
on the Spark url this time

auth-get-sso-cookie -vv -u "https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:18080" -o
auth

curl -Lb auth "https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:18080"

curl -Lb auth "https://ithdpdev-ekleszcz01.cern.ch:8443/spark3history"
```

Knox rewrite rules

Knox rewrite rules are a bit tricky to understand but then easy to maintain. You have 2 types of rewrite rules, IN and OUT.

IN: Every URL that Knox intercepts which goes from the user to one service For example clicking on a link of a proxied service, we might have a rewrite rule that rewrite the request to the service itself

OUT: Every URL that Knox intercepts which goes from the server to the user For example href links on an html page, we might want to rewrite those to point somewhere else either to the service itself or to Knox proxy

To get a better understanding of those rules you can check the following presentation and documentations:

- [Summer student project final presentation](#)
- [Understanding Rewrite Rules for Apache Knox](#)
- [Adding a service to Apache Knox](#)
- [Knox Dev guide rewrite filters](#)

:warning: Rewrite rules are generating files in /usr/hdp/knox/data/deployments make sure you delete everything inside of that when you modify the rewrite rules so that you see your modifications. Those files are generating when restarting the service

Knox HA

To enable Knox HA, we need to make sure we copy the `{GATEWAY_HOME}/data/security/keystores/{TOPOLOGY_NAME}-credentials.jcks` from the master to the other nodes

Once you configured your first master node, you can now create the following directory on node 2 that we will scp from 1 to 2

```
# On server 2
mkdir /etc/knox

# Back on server 1
scp -r /etc/knox/ root@<host2>:/etc/
scp -r /usr/hdp/knox-2.0.0/ root@<host2>:/usr/hdp/

# On server 2

mkdir /etc/alternatives/knox
ln -s /etc/alternatives/knox /usr/hdp/knox
ln -s /usr/hdp/knox-2.0.0/ /etc/alternatives/knox
chown -R <usr non root user> /usr/hdp/knox/*
export GATEWAY=/usr/hdp/knox/bin/gateway.sh
```

Here is the chosen HA architecture chosen because it was simpler to do and to maintain and provides enough HA for the moment. With this one we are installing Knox only on the 2 namenodes of the cluster.

We also can have HA as a star shape pattern since each Knox instance is independent and only provides proxy mechanism we could install Knox on each node of a given cluster to get more HA then with only 2 but we didn't choose that architecture because it is a little bit more complex to maintain and overkill for what we currently need.

Another architecture could be to install Knox on different machines out of the cluster, than to manage multiple cluster with it. Even though this architecture might be nice in theory it also provides a single point of failure for every cluster.

ACLs

Knox as a build in ACL provider allowing you to whitelist users, groups or even IP address to access some services. This is very well documented [here](#).

In our case we are going to use the application portal [role system](#) which works fine. Allowing us to define roles that should have access to our Apache Knox cluster

Auditing

Out of the box Knox provide auditing on everything that happens. All the logs are stored in logs/gateway-audit.log and here is what they look like:

```
/08/14 09:10:28
||e2560c9f-ad47-4e08-bfb9-6573548c0488|audit|194.12.154.214|HDFSUI|tmauran|||authenticati
on|uri|/gateway/default/hdfs/|success|
```

[Here](#) is a table to know how to read each line.

Metrics

Apache Knox offers metrics available when you create a new health.xml topology with the role HEALTH as [follows](#).

To enable metrics, you also need to add the following parameters in the gateway-site.xml configuration:

```
<property>
  <name>gateway.metrics.enabled</name>
  <value>true</value>
  <description>Boolean flag indicates whether to enable the metrics
collection</description>
</property>

<property>
  <name>gateway.jmx.metrics.reporting.enabled</name>
  <value>true</value>
  <description>Boolean flag indicates whether to enable the metrics
reporting using JMX</description>
</property>
```

The metrics will then be available on the /gateway/health/v1/metrics route where you will find a big JSON with different very useful information. You should try to navigate to many pages through the homepage and you will see the timers for each component that will increase, for example:

```
▼ client./gateway/default/hdfs/.GET-requests:
  count: 3
  max: 0.029422862
  mean: 0.014998260520212059
  min: 0.006354107
  p50: 0.009983171
  p75: 0.029422862
  p95: 0.029422862
  p98: 0.029422862
  p99: 0.029422862
  p999: 0.029422862
  stddev: 0.010047081784954372
  m15_rate: 0.4135206418274288
  m1_rate: 0.0022560067414953144
  m5_rate: 0.1964215251718366
  mean_rate: 0.0087025342450983
  duration_units: "seconds"
  rate_units: "calls/second"
```

Current Knox architecture

Automatization of the project

At the end of the project, significant efforts were directed towards the automation of the entire configuration and deployment process using Puppet, ensuring that the setup of Apache Knox and the secure access to Hadoop services could be consistently and efficiently replicated across different environments. Additionally, a custom repository was established to manage the build process for RPM packages using CERN's Koji system. This approach not only streamlined the deployment of Knox, but also facilitated ongoing maintenance and updates, reducing manual intervention and minimizing the risk of configuration drift. The automation and RPM packaging efforts were crucial in integrating Apache Knox into CERN's infrastructure, ensuring a scalable and maintainable solution for securing Hadoop services.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the project successfully implemented Apache Knox to secure various Hadoop web services at CERN, replacing the existing SPNEGO-based security framework. The transition to Knox addressed several challenges associated with SPNEGO, including complex browser configurations and inconsistent user experiences. By providing a centralized authentication and access point, Knox not only enhanced the security of the Hadoop ecosystem but also significantly improved usability for end-users.

The project also demonstrated the importance of a flexible security architecture, leveraging Knox's topology-based configuration and rewrite rules to protect key services such as HBaseUI, YARNUI, HDFSUI, and the Spark History Server. Despite initial setup complexities and the need for custom solutions to handle specific challenges, such as CORS issues with the Spark History Server, Knox proved to be a robust and scalable solution.

Furthermore, the automation of the deployment process using Puppet, coupled with the creation of a custom RPM repository via the Koji system, ensured that the Knox-based security setup could be easily maintained and replicated. This automation not only streamlined the deployment but also reduced the potential for errors and configuration inconsistencies, contributing to the long-term sustainability of the solution.

On a personal note, this project was an invaluable learning experience. Working in such a dynamic and innovative environment at CERN allowed me to gain deep insights into both security architecture and automation practices. I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor, Emil Kleszcz, for his guidance and support throughout the project. His mentorship played a crucial role in the successful completion of this work, and I am deeply appreciative of the opportunity to learn and grow under his supervision.

Overall, the project achieved its goals of enhancing security, improving user experience, and providing a maintainable and scalable solution for securing Hadoop services at CERN. The successful implementation and automation of Apache Knox mark a significant step forward in the security management of the organization's Hadoop infrastructure.

Useful resources

JIRA boards

[Hadoop JIRA board](#)

[Knox JIRA board](#)

[Spark JIRA board](#)

[HBase JIRA board](#)

Mailing lists

[Archives](#)

Cloudera forum

[Forum](#)